

Ecklonia maxima

Sea bamboo

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Group: Algae

Size: Typically, 1.5 m to 10 m in height.

Distribution:

Ecklonia maxima grows from just north of Luderitz in Namibia to De Hoop in the Western Cape province of South Africa.

Importance:

Ecklonia maxima is a dominant species along the south-west African coast, where it forms extensive kelp forests that are important hubs of marine biodiversity. It is commercially harvested for the production of plant biostimulants used in agriculture and as a food source for farmed abalone.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 24.8 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 28.42 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.8 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 74.4%, Duplicated: 25.2%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 3 024.02 kilobases

Contig number: 2 159

Sample Contributor contact details:

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